

THE ESSENCE OF PROFESSIONALLY ORIGINAL WORK IN THE CONDITIONS OF AN EDUCATIONAL CLUSTER

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Abstract. *Based on the main goal of the education reform of our republic, special attention is being paid to the use of modern information technologies, popularization of best practices taking into account people's capabilities, individual qualities, level of intellectual development, and further improvement of the quality of career guidance in the content of general education.*

Keywords: *educational cluster, career choice, educational reform, vocational orientation, information technology, individual quality, intellectual development, competent approach, social partnership, network cooperation.*

Introduction:

Recently, the concept of "educational cluster" has been used very often in pedagogical and psychological literature. In the framework of "New values of education", the educational cluster is understood as a "system" existing in society, where relations are established subjectively, in which special activities of various systems (state, public and mixed) are carried out for the development of the individual and his socialization, free choice of profession. Also, an internally formed, individual educational direction, a professional direction, which occurs through experience, can be formed.

The most common understanding of the field of education is educational clusters (or systems), which are presented as a set of individual forms of development and diversity of learning opportunities. Clustering a group of children-adults, a class, or a school allows, first of all, to include them in a field of opportunities and choices embedded in the wider social field (simultaneous implementation). Secondly, views of pedagogical activities in a pair (teacher-student) are improved.

Research and analyze:

The ideas and views of F. Frebel [1], M. Montessori [2], R. Steiner [3], J. Piaget [4] play an important role in guiding children to the profession. Systematic work is being carried out by them on early career guidance, development of children's abilities from preschool education, determination of quality indicators of education, formation of career ideas and concepts in children through game technologies.

R. Slavin [6], E. Bern [7] etc. researched the modern trends of formation of interest in profession among young people abroad.

Solving these tasks in the conditions of an educational cluster serves to create the necessary pedagogical conditions for choosing the right profession. Based on the main goal of the educational reform of our republic, there is a need to use modern information technologies to increase the efficiency of vocational training, popularize best practices taking into account people's capabilities, individual qualities, intellectual development level, and further improve the quality of vocational training in the content of general education.

Currently, more than 20,000 educational institutions around the world are operating using the methodology of the Italian pedagogue Maria Montessori (1870-1952). M. Montessori is characterized by the individual and emotional orientation of the child, his pace of development, physical and mental needs. M. Montessori's methodology is based on the natural stimulation of the child's personal motivation towards learning, while reducing the management of adults as much as possible, creating a developmental environment equipped with special didactic materials for the child. In this environment, common things are used, as a result of their use, the child's enthusiasm for learning the environment increases [2].

The simplicity and popularity of the methodology is that allowing the child to participate in family chores, such as cleaning the house, repairing, collecting his toys, allows him to play with the above-mentioned things with a view to his intellectual development.

The German pedagogue R.Steiner (1861-1925) is the founder of Waldorf pedagogy, which focuses on the intellectual development of the child in contrast to traditional education, in which the goal is to develop the child comprehensively through science, art, ethics and religious values [3].

From a pedagogical point of view, it should be noted that educational clusters determine the subject of education, a complex and multi-level field organization, and self-organization performs the task of self-organization, providing a connection between a simple empirical image of an educational institution (as an institution) and its vision as a system.

Educational clusters can be considered as a sphere of human learning through joint life activities and meetings of all age groups, determination of joint (social) life goals, and participation in it. This new form of education requires us to rethink our traditional ideas about it. Education is the way and form of formation as a person in the sphere of culture and history, acquisition of a human image. Therefore, according to V.I. Slobodchikov, three main tasks are solved in the field of education:

1. Taking root by forming a meaningful way of life and activity of people in a certain cultural-historical field and eliminating the current situation of people;
2. Creating opportunities for people to live in communities that do not leave people without shelter;
3. Cultivating a culture that does not allow egocentric capriciousness among people and relativism within cultures, and conveys valuable images of life and forms of life to generations [8].

The introduction of a competent approach to the educational process requires the creation of a more developed system of extracurricular activities of students by expanding the scope of vocational guidance, which in turn requires the development of social partnership and network cooperation of the school with a wide range of institutions and organizations in the open society. Forming a single cultural and educational field of the school around the learner allows to maximize his creative abilities and build an individual educational direction taking into account his interests, inclinations and needs. Educational clusters are increasingly required to solve this problem.

Research results:

The analysis of experiences on the activity of educational clusters in solving the current problems facing the educational system indicates the possibilities and effectiveness of repetition. Identification and wide implementation of the recommended models of building the cultural and

educational sphere of the school will allow enriching the local practice of management of educational institutions with new effective tools.

It is known that in recent years, the development of an algorithm for managing career guidance processes (M. Yu. Makarova [7]) for the information system in the direction of diagnosis and counseling of the educational aspects of career guidance is gaining importance. This problem is also related to career guidance, and we believe that it is necessary to form initial ideas about new professions in students at each stage of education. Because the emergence of new professions and the disappearance of some professions affect the needs of students to choose a profession.

The concept of guiding students to a profession in the educational process includes such concepts as "Profession", "Professional education", "Profession orientation", "Vocational information", "Early career orientation", "Polytechnic education", "Profession introduction".

The following rules should be observed in the formation of labor skills in children:

- 1) organization of types of work related to nature, such as self-service, farm work, plowing, planting seedlings, watering seedlings, as well as manual labor;
- 2) full use of the time allocated for work, regular involvement of students in types of work;
- 3) use of individual and collective types of labor activity;
- 4) choosing the methods and methods of guiding students' work in accordance with the educational tasks;
- 5) reasonable combination of types of work with other types of children's activities;
- 6) such as providing an environment for students to be interested in the profession.

If the work of all students is properly organized through the agenda, they will feel great joy from it.

Cultivating students' creative attitude to work and profession, forming them as highly moral, free-thinking individuals and providing education is a requirement of the times.

In the new conditions of the continuous education system and the development of personnel training, the main goal of guiding students to the profession is to prepare each student-graduate to consciously choose a profession and continue education in the chosen field.

Conclusion:

As the period of development of an adult person becomes harmonious with the process of orientation to a profession, his development process takes place under the influence of educational clusters. The teacher should conduct vocational guidance in the conditions of the educational cluster, taking into account the individual abilities of the student and paying attention to various technical systems and technologies for directing them to various professions and their ability to resolve conflicts in the laws of development.

The technology of guiding students to the profession is a pedagogical process, and it is appropriate to provide it through educational clusters as a project of a certain pedagogical system, which is required to be introduced into practice or a process that serves to change a certain situation. The results of the work of educational clusters can be positively evaluated in the work of career orientation only if young people have the skills to identify needs in various spheres of life, plan their activities taking into account the requirements of the scientific organization of work, and look for new solutions after seeing the final result of their activities.

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